

Silicon Photonic MEMS Chip for Photothermal Spectroscopy Gas Sensing

Ahmed Mahrous^{1,2,3}, Mazen Erfan^{2,3}, Johannes P. Waclawek⁴, Ahmed Mostafa¹, Nicolas Pavy¹, Frédéric Marty¹, Elyes Nefzaoui¹, Yasser M. Sabry^{2,3}, Bernhard Lendl⁴, Tarik Bourouina¹,

1. ESYCOM Lab, Univ Gustave Eiffel, CNRS, F-77454 Marne-la-Vallée, France

2. Si-Ware Systems SAS, 16 rue Portalis, 75008 Paris, France

3. Faculty of Engineering, Ain-Shams University, 1 Elsarayat St., 11535 Abbaseya, Cairo, Egypt

4. Institute of Chemical Technologies and Analytics, TU Wien, Vienna 1060, Austria

Photothermal spectroscopy (PTS) [1-4] emerges as an excellent alternative to direct absorption spectroscopy and to photoacoustic spectroscopy, especially for high sensitivity gas sensing, with demonstrated lower limits of detection (LLOD) from ppm down to sub-ppb gas concentration levels [1-2]. A Fabry-Pérot Interferometer (FPI) can be used as the core sensing element for PTS. A first infrared laser beam (excitation) is injected to the FPI cavity to induce gas absorption. Its wavelength is chosen at a specific absorption line of the target gas. Light absorption by the gas causes local heating within the cavity, which translates into a variation of refractive index and hence, a shift of the FPI resonant wavelengths. This shift is detected by operating the FPI at fixed wavelength near resonance, using another near-infrared (probe) laser beam. This shift causes a variation of intensity of the transmitted and reflected probe light. In this operation scheme, the FPI requirements include both high finesse and high throughput, which are not trivial to attain, when targeting extreme miniaturization [4] at low cost, which would benefit for large-scale deployment of PTS that includes optical fiber communication networks [3].

This opportunity and related challenges are the motivations for this work aiming to study the potential of silicon micro-FPI for their operation in PTS gas sensing. To this end, we designed and fabricated a Photonic Integrated Circuit (PIC) as shown in Figure 1. It includes an array of FPIs, although only one is sufficient for PTS operation. All FPIs are made solely from single-crystalline silicon as the result of silicon micromachining. Both FPI mirrors are Bragg Reflectors, which consist of silicon-air dielectric multilayers [5]. The FPI is open to allow surrounding gas to circulate within the cavity. It is designed to accommodate both free-space and fiber light coupling. First optical fibers are positioned in the chip along aligned U-grooves. They allow easy coupling of near-infrared light. Notably, not only the probe laser but also the excitation laser can be carried through such fibers. However, for more sensitive gas sensing, it is advantageous to rely on mid-infrared lasers for the excitation light. In this case, excitation light is injected perpendicular to the chip. A through-hole in the chip and in its package enables such operation. Notably, FPI cavity length of 1 mm is chosen to accommodate for reliable perpendicular coupling of the MIR beam. This is a compromise, especially as 1 mm is not ideal for reaching high finesse considering the small lateral dimensions of the FPI mirrors, which introduce diffraction losses. Figure 1b also shows measurements of the FPI spectral response recorded using a tunable laser connected to an input fiber and an optical power-meter connected to the output fiber. The resulting quality factor Q ranges between 3000 and 6000 for resonant modes at 1550 nm wavelength, which is a promising result especially considering the miniaturization constraints. Additional experiments are underway to evaluate the sensitivity to ambient gas and will be shown during the conference. This is expected to be the first demonstration of PTS gas sensing based on a silicon FPI.

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic concept of a silicon Photonic Integrated Circuit embedding FPIs designed for operation in PTS gas sensing. (b) Fabricated device packaged with optical-fibers and corresponding measurement of the spectral transmittance.

References

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